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Strengthening cross-border cooperation in a living Europe: Policy recommendations for the SaarLorLux border region

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FUNDING NOTICE

This *Policy Paper* summarises the results of a research project on assessments made by municipal decision-makers in the SaarLorLux region regarding cooperation in the joint border region and a European Union that is alive at the local level. The project was funded by the Saarland State Chancellery in 2024 and 2025. The authors would like to express their gratitude for the financial support.

STRENGTHENING CROSS-BORDER COOPERATION IN A LIVING EUROPE: POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE SAARLORLUX BORDER REGION

Close cross-border relationships and interdependencies have developed in recent decades in the SaarLorLux border region, and these are crucially linked to the European integration process. However, it is also evident that further deepening of cross-border cooperation requires new impetus and can be hindered by nationalist-populist forces. Based on quantitative and qualitative surveys of municipal decision-makers conducted in 2024 in Saarland (Germany), *département* Moselle (France), and the Grand Duchy of Luxembourg, this *Policy Paper* provides an overview of six key areas of action, with corresponding policy recommendations. These areas are: (1) accelerating existing efforts in education and language; (2) reducing bureaucratic hurdles; (3) strengthening municipal competencies; (4) being closer to citizens; (5) adopting pragmatic procedures; and (6) enabling cross-border cooperation in all areas. Europe, and specifically the EU, stands for cooperation that transcends borders, but this requires significant commitment and appropriate opportunities.

STÄRKUNG DER GRENZÜBERSCHREITENDEN KOOPERATION IM GELEBTEN EUROPA: POLITISCHE HANDLUNGSEMPFEHLUNGEN FÜR DIE GRENZREGION SAARLORLUX

In der Grenzregion SaarLorLux haben sich in den letzten Jahrzehnten enge grenzüberschreitende Beziehungen und Verwobenheiten entwickelt, die auf entscheidende Weise mit dem europäischen Integrationsprozess verbunden sind. Gleichzeitig zeigt sich, dass grenzüberschreitende Kooperation zum einen für weitere Vertiefungen noch einmal neue Impulse benötigt und zum anderen von nationalistisch-populistischen Bestrebungen auch konterkariert und beeinträchtigt werden kann. Basierend auf quantitativen und qualitativen Erhebungen von kommunalen Entscheidungsträgern im Saarland (Deutschland), dem *département* Moselle (Frankreich) und dem Großherzogtum Luxemburg im Jahr 2024 skizziert das *Policy Paper* sechs zentrale Handlungsbedarfe mit politischen Empfehlungen: Es bedarf einer (1) Forcierung bestehender Anstrengungen in den Bereichen Bildung und Sprache, (2) einer Reduktion bürokratischer Hürden, (3) einer Stärkung kommunaler Kompetenzen, (4) mehr Bürgernähe und (5) pragmatischer Verfahrensweisen, wobei es insgesamt um (6) eine Ermöglichung grenzüberschreitender Kooperation in allen Bereichen gehen sollte. Europa und konkret die EU stehen für ein Miteinander, das grenzüberschreitend vorgelebt werden kann – aber eben nicht als Selbstläufer, sondern als Perspektive, die durchgehend großes Engagement und die passenden Möglichkeiten mit sich bringt.

RENFORCER LA COOPERATION TRANSFRONTALIERE DANS L'EUROPE VECUE : RECOMMANDATIONS D'ACTION POLITIQUE POUR LA REGION FRONTALIERE SAARLORLUX

Les étroites relations et interdépendances transfrontalières qui se sont tissées dans la région frontalière SaarLorLux sont liées de manière déterminante au processus d'intégration européenne. Parallèlement, il apparaît, d'une part, que la coopération transfrontalière nécessite d'un nouvel élan pour de plus amples approfondissements et, d'autre part, qu'elle peut être contrecarrée et entravée par des aspirations nationalistes et populistes. Sur la base d'enquêtes quantitatives et qualitatives menées auprès de décideurs communaux de la Sarre (Allemagne), du département de la Moselle (France) et du Grand-Duché de Luxembourg en 2024, le *Policy Paper* identifie six domaines d'actions centrales assorties de recommandations politiques. Il est nécessaire (1) d'accélérer les efforts existants dans les domaines de l'éducation et des langues, (2) de réduire les obstacles bureaucratiques, (3) de renforcer les compétences communales, (4) de se rapprocher des citoyens et (5) de mettre en place des procédures pragmatiques. L'objectif global est (6) de faciliter la coopération transfrontalière dans tous les domaines. L'Europe, et plus concrètement l'UE, sont synonymes d'une cohabitation qui peut être vécue par-delà les frontières, non pas comme une évidence qui va de soi, mais plutôt comme une perspective qui nécessite un grand engagement sans relâche et des possibilités appropriées.

ADDRESSES

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1. Cross-border cooperation in the SaarLorLux region

SaarLorLux, as a historically grown part of the so-called Greater Region, is a prime example of the diverse opportunities and challenges of cross-border cooperation in Europe. In many areas of political, economic and social life, we can look back on a long tradition of exchange and networking across national borders (Lorig et al., 2016a; Weber & Dittel, 2025; Weber & Dörrenbächer, 2022; Wille, 2015). At the same time, there are still areas where action is needed; these are evident in everyday life and make it necessary to take a closer look at the concept of well-functioning cooperation (Crossey & Weber, 2021; Damm, 2018; Dittel & Weber, 2025). The Covid-19 pandemic demonstrated that things we take for granted, such as open borders, can also be revoked (Brodowski et al., 2023; Wassenberg, 2020; Weber et al., 2021; Wille & Kanesu, 2020). Today in 2025, 12 of the 29 Schengen area countries are controlling their national borders again. Did the pandemic, then, serve as a real-life laboratory demonstrating that European borders can indeed be controlled long term? 40 years after the Schengen Agreement, new obstacles to cross-border living are clearly emerging: after all, easily passable borders are crucial for cross-border commuters, among others (Brodowski et al., 2025; Wille, 2025).

The European Commission's (2021) postulate of border regions as living labs of European integration can, then, be questioned from various perspectives (see also Bertram et al., 2023; Braun et al., 2025). At the same time, this vision must be brought to life if border regions are to fulfil this function as spaces that make an important contribution to the EU. At the local level the achievements of the EU can be experienced in a very tangible way. This is where "interfaces of growth" – "Nahtstellen des Zusammenwachsens" – can emerge in Europe, as Saarland's Premier Anke Rehlinger (2023, p.9) emphasised in her government statement ahead of the 60th anniversary of the Élysée Treaty in 2023. It is the regional and local levels that are of particular importance in this respect (Dittel & Weber, 2024; Peyrony, 2024).

In 2024, surveys by the European Studies Working Group at Saarland University, funded by the Saarland State Chancellery, focused specifically on the municipal level in the SaarLorLux border region (detailed in German and French in Dittel & Weber, 2025). The question they asked was: Where, from the perspective of local decision-makers, do cross-border relations in the SaarLorLux region stand now, at some distance from the turning point of the pandemic of spring 2020? What paths can be taken for future cross-border cooperation? And what prospects does this open up for Europe? This *Policy Paper* brings together key recommendations for action arising from the study. An overview of the methodological approach and key findings is followed by six central areas of recommendation and a brief conclusion.

2. Methodological approach

The study is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to assess cross-border relations in the SaarLorLux region from a grass-roots perspective in their significance for a lived Europe. In spring 2024, six semi-structured, guided interviews were conducted with eight municipal representatives from Saarland, *département* Moselle, and the Grand Duchy of Luxembourg. The interviews, which lasted an average of 60 minutes, were conducted in person or via video conference. The interviewees were free to choose the language of the interview (German or French). In addition, an online survey was conducted in summer 2024 among mayors in all 52 municipalities in Saarland, 151 randomly selected municipalities in Moselle, and all 100 municipalities in Luxembourg. The response rate was 56% (Saarland), 37% (Moselle) and 40% (Luxembourg). The three separate surveys of the sub-regions made it possible to evaluate the responses separately and to draw comparisons. At the end of the survey, the mayors were asked to provide their postcode on a voluntary basis so that the municipalities could be ordered according to whether they were located directly on the border or not (for details, see Dittel & Weber, 2025, pp.7–9).

3. Key empirical findings

The mayors surveyed in Saarland, the *département* Moselle, and the Grand Duchy of Luxembourg associate Europe especially with open borders and freedom of travel, peace, the monetary union, and solidarity. It follows that the ability to cross national borders freely within the Schengen area is seen as an essential feature. Cross-border cooperation is also of vital importance to the mayors surveyed. There is a high level of agreement with the metaphor of the border region as a living lab of European integration (full agreement 31% Saarland, 30% Moselle, 41% Luxembourg), but this is tempered by practical obstacles. The ideal and the reality are not yet seen as entirely congruent. Nevertheless, the general sense of attachment to Europe is high. The survey results show an overall positive attitude towards mutual connectedness. The location of the municipalities is a particularly important variable here: When a distinction is made between municipalities directly bordering a neighbouring country or countries and other municipalities, it becomes apparent that representatives of border municipalities express a very strong attachment to Europe (56%), compared with 32% in non-border municipalities. The same is true when looking at attachment to the border region: Here, as many as 67% of mayors from border municipalities feel very close ties, compared to 28% of those without a direct border location. The results also illustrate that a good half of the municipalities that took part in the survey have partnerships with municipalities in neighbouring countries as a basis for exchange across national borders. Cooperation now takes place in a wide range of areas: mutual visits to ceremonies and festive occasions are at the forefront, followed by informal mutual visits, joint events, exchanges between associations, cooperation in the tourism sector and between fire brigades, as well as other areas. This results in a field ranging from informal exchanges to formalised forms of cooperation. Cross-border cooperation is the result of the historical development of the border region, close ties, and a European mindset, among other things – but it cannot be taken for granted.

All three sub-regions cite very similar challenges as barriers:

- other tasks dominating day-to-day business
- high bureaucratic effort in acquiring funding for cross-border exchange
- different financial resources in Saarland, Moselle, and Luxembourg
- limited financial and human resources in the municipalities
- language barriers
- different distribution of responsibilities and competencies (federal versus predominantly centralised systems).

The Covid-19 pandemic highlighted the vulnerability of cross-border structures. Increased border controls and the temporary closure of various border crossings, as well as insufficiently coordinated top-down measures, led to a loss of trust and the need to strengthen established cooperation with even greater commitment. At the same time, the importance of cross-border solidarity became clear, for example, through a joint Covid-19 testing centre or the transfer of Covid-19 patients. Looking back, the pandemic is seen more as a setback (36% in Saarland, 48% in Moselle, 43% in Luxembourg) than as a boost (12% in Saarland, 26% in Moselle, 18% in Luxembourg) for cross-border cooperation. However, it raised general awareness of the need for coordination. From a local perspective, the future of Europe will not be decided in Brussels or the capitals alone – it will be shaped at the interfaces of cross-border coexistence.

4. Recommendations for political action

The results of the study identify six areas in which there is a need for improvement and adjustment – areas recommended for political action. These are: education and language, reduction of bureaucratic obstacles, strengthening of municipal competencies, closer contact with citizens, pragmatic procedures, and openness towards cross-border cooperation (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Overview of areas recommended for political action

Source: Own compilation and visualisation 2025.

Education and language

A key finding is the high demand for structured educational programmes to promote the neighbouring language in Saarland/*département* Moselle in order to break down language barriers. This should start early in the pre-school and school sectors, with an expansion of French/German lessons, supported by student exchanges, in order to achieve the same level of German, French and English language skills as in Luxembourg. Language courses should also be offered later in life so that the skills learned are not lost. With regard to the municipalities, this means offering language courses for employees. Local government representatives perceive a lack of language skills as a growing challenge, so this is an area where action is needed. Cross-border educational cooperation must be intensified and multilingualism promoted as a strategic pillar of cross-border cooperation.

Reduction of bureaucratic obstacles

The high administrative burden is one of the biggest challenges facing cross-border project work. In all three sub-regions, bureaucracy was cited as one of the main obstacles. The application procedures for the Interreg programme, for example, are considered too complex and resource-intensive. To change this, it is recommended that application and accounting processes be simplified and digitised. In addition, adapted legal and administrative provisions, like those contained in the Treaty of Aachen (Art. 13) (Bundesrepublik Deutschland & Französische Republik, 2019), should be actively promoted and implemented in order to achieve cross-border simplifications (see also Beck, 2022). Furthermore, new laws at national level must be reviewed in advance for their impact on border regions – keyword: border region check.

Strengthening of municipal competencies

Local authorities are key players in cross-border relations. At the same time, they are subject to restrictions due to limited legal powers. In the quantitative survey, over 80% of respondents called for regional and local powers to be strengthened. Accordingly, it is recommended that local decision-making powers be expanded, particularly in matters of cooperation, and that new and permanent financing instruments be made available for project implementation. Local authorities must be given clear responsibilities and sufficient resources to enable them to act in a European dimension. This must be followed by stronger lobbying at European and national levels for local authority concerns.

Closer contact with citizens

Cross-border cooperation has become increasingly institutionalised in recent years, but this has led to accusations of executive dominance, for example in the Greater Region (Lorig et al., 2016b, p.39). Against this backdrop, concrete benefits must be tangible and perceptible for the local population. Cross-border cooperation must therefore be reflected in people's everyday lives – this applies to public transport, healthcare, vocational training, and climate protection, among other things. Greater citizen involvement is becoming a key concept. Support programmes should prioritise measures that offer immediate and tangible added value. Local authorities should, therefore, be supported at a higher level in planning and implementing these projects together with civil society actors. Cross-border cooperation projects should focus more on the concrete realities of people's lives. It is crucial to involve the population and allow them to participate in project development (see also Landeshauptstadt Saarbrücken & Communauté d'Agglomération Forbach, 2025).

Pragmatic procedures

The recommendations for action from a municipal perspective outlined above give rise to more pragmatic procedures. These have to involve action that focuses on opportunities for simplification, as was the case at times during the first phase of the Covid-19 pandemic, when solutions were sought and found beyond the confines of rigid regulations. This could lead to the establishment of a cross-border health corridor, for example, in the future. Procedures that make life easier for local residents should be less complicated, less bureaucratic and more citizen-friendly. Creative, pragmatic solutions should not be sacrificed to rigid regulations. The political objective must be to reduce obstacles and increase scope for action.

Openness towards cross-border cooperation

Finally, local representatives express their desire for a fundamentally enabling attitude towards cross-border cooperation. In principle, there should no longer be any area where cross-border cooperation, insofar as it is desired by citizens, local authorities or governments, is not feasible. Instead of looking for objections, all energy should be devoted to finding regulations that take account of everyday cross-border life and turn border regions into genuine laboratories for Europe. Ultimately, a proactive attitude towards cross-border cooperation must become the guiding principle at all political levels in order to make a Europe of lived experience even more of a reality.

5. Conclusion

The SaarLorLux region demonstrates in various areas how cross-border cooperation can succeed – provided that the political framework, resources, and commitment are coordinated. In order to fully exploit the potential, targeted political and institutional decisions are needed. The results and recommendations for action presented here make it clear that cross-border cooperation does not work by itself, but requires active shaping and support. A policy of enabling is needed that is not limited to symbolic commitments but aims at structural implementation and enforcement: through better resource allocation to local authorities, adapted rules on responsibilities, and cross-border coordination mechanisms.

From the perspective of local decision-makers, border regions can and should serve as role models and living labs for the EU, because what works locally should also work on a larger scale. Going beyond the laboratory idea, border regions are becoming a practical testing ground for growing together and living together in Europe. Cross-border cooperation can and must be promoted and strengthened from the bottom up, but this can only succeed with support from EU, national, and regional levels. If the trend towards ever tighter border controls in the EU continues, undermining the European idea of open borders and slowing down cross-border cooperation, there is a risk that border regions will not function as beacons of European integration, but will become, as Chilla puts it (2022, n.p.), museums of European history.

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